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LCISS is intended for scholars who wish to report results of completed or on-going research, reviews of literature and discussions of theoretical issues or policy. Its primary objective is to provide a forum for the exchange of the ideas across disciplines and academic orientations in the social sciences.

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Promoting Inclusive Education for Children with Disabilities in Ibadan Metropolis: The Role of Community-Based Social Work

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Abstract

This study examines the pivotal role of community-based social work in fostering inclusive education for children with disabilities in Nigeria. Inclusive education is not only a fundamental human right but also a key pillar for social development and equity. However, children with disabilities in low-resource settings, particularly in Ibadan, continue to encounter systemic barriers such as infrastructural limitations, cultural stigma, inadequate teacher training, and poor policy implementation, all of which hinder their access to meaningful participation and quality education. Grounded in a qualitative research design, the study adopted a purposive sampling technique to select respondents from both public and private special education institutions in Ibadan, including HLA Special Education School, School for the Handicapped Sharp-Corner, Omoyeni School for Handicapped, and AIKEA Special School and Home. A total of 15 in-depth interviews were conducted with key stakeholders, including social workers, school administrators, and teachers of children with disabilities. Data was collected using semi-structured interview guides and was analyzed thematically to extract meaningful patterns and insights. Findings revealed that community-based social workers play a pivotal role in bridging the gap between families, schools, and government agencies by advocating for accessible learning environments, facilitating parental involvement, and coordinating support services. Despite challenges such as limited funding, training gaps, cultural stigma, and inadequate policy implementation, social workers employ innovative approaches, including home-based interventions, community outreach, and multi-stakeholder collaboration, to promote inclusive education. The study concludes that empowering social workers and strengthening community-based systems are essential to achieving inclusive education for children with disabilities in Nigeria.

Keywords: Inclusive Education, Children with Disabilities, Community-Based Social Work, Special Needs Schools, Qualitative Research, Ibadan.

Introduction

Inclusive education is recognized globally as a fundamental human right and a cornerstone for achieving equitable, accessible, and quality education for all learners, regardless of their physical, intellectual, emotional, or social challenges. It is grounded in the principle that every child, including those with disabilities, should be able to learn in an environment that accommodates their individual learning needs and supports their full development. The ideology of inclusive education extends beyond merely placing children with disabilities in mainstream schools; it involves a systemic transformation of educational systems to ensure that all children are respected, welcomed, and valued (UNESCO, 2020).

The **United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD)**, adopted in 2006, significantly elevated the global conversation on inclusive education. Article 24 of the convention mandates state parties to ensure inclusive education systems at all levels, recognizing the right of persons with disabilities to education without discrimination and on the basis of equal opportunity (United Nations, 2006). The convention insists that people with disabilities should not be excluded from the general education system based on disability and that reasonable accommodation must be provided to meet their individual needs. This global commitment compels member states, including Nigeria, to align their national policies and practices with the principles of inclusive education.

In the Nigerian context, particularly in urban centers such as Ibadan, these policy intentions are often not translated into practical realities for children with disabilities. Many public and private schools remain under-equipped to support inclusive learning. Facilities such as ramps, assistive technology, trained special education teachers, and individualized learning materials are either unavailable or insufficient (Okechukwu & Ekpenyong, 2020). Teachers in regular schools often lack the training needed to adapt curricula or teaching strategies to accommodate children with various disabilities. Additionally, the deep-rooted cultural stigmatization of disabilities continues to create significant psychological and emotional barriers for both learners and their families (Abang, 2005).

Community-based social work emerges as a pivotal and transformative strategy for overcoming the multifaceted barriers that hinder the successful implementation of inclusive education for children with disabilities in Nigeria. Rooted in the principles of empowerment, participation, and social justice, community-based social work promotes collaborative approaches by engaging diverse stakeholders' families, educators, community leaders, and policymakers in the pursuit of inclusive and equitable education systems (United Nations Children's Fund [UNICEF], 2013). In environments such as Ibadan, where systemic inequalities persist between public and private institutions, the presence of social workers within communities becomes even more critical in bridging service delivery gaps.

Social workers bridge schools and families, support children with disabilities, and enforce inclusive education policies. They mediate, educate caregivers on their rights, and collaborate with schools for necessary adjustments (Mmatli, 2008).

This study explores community-based social work's vital role in advancing inclusive education for children with disabilities in Ibadan, Nigeria. It explores how social workers collaborate with parents, educators, and policymakers in special education settings to enhance access and support. Through qualitative data, the study reveals effective practices, systemic challenges, and opportunities for enhancing inclusive education through collaborative efforts. By promoting empowerment and inclusion, social workers can foster integration, enhance learning outcomes, and combat stigmatization in educational settings (Mmatli, 2008; UNICEF, 2013). This research contributes to the inclusive education dialogue in low-resource urban areas, such as Ibadan.

Literature Review

Inclusive education is a pedagogical and philosophical orientation that asserts the right of every child to receive quality education in a mainstream setting, regardless of their physical, cognitive, social, emotional, linguistic, or cultural background (UNESCO, 2009). It is rooted in the principles of equity, participation, and respect for diversity. Inclusive education goes beyond integrating children with disabilities into regular classrooms; it is about transforming the education system to accommodate all learners, particularly those who are marginalized or excluded. According to Ainscow and Miles (2008), inclusion should not be misconstrued as a placement strategy limited to individuals with disabilities. Rather, it is a dynamic and ongoing process that entails addressing and responding to the diverse needs of all learners by increasing participation in learning environments, school culture, and community activities.

Globally, the right to inclusive education has been recognized in several international instruments such as the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD, 2006), which mandates state parties to ensure that persons with disabilities have access to inclusive, quality, and free primary and secondary education in the communities in which they live. The Sustainable Development Goals (SDG 4) further reaffirm this commitment by emphasizing inclusive and equitable quality education for all. These global frameworks have informed national policies across many countries, including Nigeria.

In Nigeria, inclusive education is supported by the National Policy on Education (Federal Republic of Nigeria [FRN], 2013), promoting the integration of children with special needs into regular schools. This aims to enhance social inclusion, combat stigma, and offer equal learning opportunities. However, implementation faces challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, a lack of teacher training in special needs education, negative societal attitudes, and poor policy enforcement. Schools often lack the necessary facilities, and teachers struggle with implementing inclusive teaching methods, which hinders effective support for diverse learners (Ajuwon, 2008; Eleweke & Rodda, 2002).

These systemic issues are further compounded in urban centers like Ibadan, where disparities in resource allocation between public and private educational institutions create additional layers of exclusion. Children with disabilities from low-income households are particularly disadvantaged, as their families may lack the financial means to enroll them in better-

equipped private special education schools. The result is a dual system in which only a fraction of children with disabilities receives the support needed to succeed academically and socially.

Given these challenges, community-based social work has emerged as a critical strategy for promoting inclusive education. Community-based social work involves engaging with individuals and groups at the grassroots level to identify local problems, advocate for social justice, and mobilize community resources to address specific needs (International Federation of Social Workers [IFSW], 2014).

Empirical Review

Empirical research on inclusive education in Nigeria reveals a persistent gap between policy formulation and actual practice. Although the National Policy on Education (FRN, 2013) provides for the integration of children with disabilities into mainstream education, the realization of inclusive education remains elusive due to multifaceted structural, institutional, and cultural challenges. Studies consistently highlight the disconnect between the theoretical ideals of inclusion and the ground realities of Nigeria's educational system.

Similarly, Eleweke and Rodda (2002) investigated infrastructural and attitudinal barriers to inclusive education in various Nigerian regions. Their findings indicated that most schools are ill-equipped to support learners with disabilities. Key issues included inadequate physical infrastructure such as ramps and accessible toilets, lack of assistive technology, and limited availability of learning materials tailored to diverse needs. More critically, teacher attitudes toward inclusion were generally negative. Many educators viewed inclusive education as burdensome and disruptive to general classroom management. These findings underline the systemic limitations that continue to impede inclusive education in Nigeria.

Community engagement, however, emerges as a crucial enabler of inclusive education in several empirical studies. Ozoji (2015), in a study carried out in northern Nigeria, found that the involvement of community stakeholders such as local NGOs, religious organizations, and parent groups significantly improved the implementation of inclusive practices. Supportive community programs effectively addressed institutional shortcomings, highlighting grassroots efforts and collective responsibility in promoting inclusive education.

In the context of Ibadan, Nigeria's third-largest city and a major educational hub, the implementation of inclusive education faces unique challenges. Adedokun (2021) conducted a comparative study between public and private schools in Ibadan and found significant disparities in terms of resources, teacher training, and accessibility. Public schools often suffer from chronic underfunding, lack of teaching aid, and an insufficient number of trained special educators. On the other hand, private schools, which are relatively better resourced, tend to be unaffordable for most families, particularly those from low socio-economic backgrounds. This creates a fragmented education system in which only a small subset of children with disabilities can access meaningful learning opportunities.

In Ibadan, despite challenges, innovative community initiatives like partnerships with special education institutions (HLA Special Education School, School for the Handicapped Sharp-

Corner, Omoyeni School for the Handicapped, AIKEA Special School and Home) promote inclusive education through activities like teacher training, providing assistive devices, and parent awareness campaigns. For instance, AIKEA Special School's collaboration with social workers includes workshops to train teachers in sign language and tactile materials, leading to improved teacher readiness and student involvement.

Theoretical Framework

This study is underpinned by the Social Model of Disability, which shifts the focus from the individual impairment to the societal and environmental barriers that hinder full participation of persons with disabilities (Michael Oliver, 1990). The Social Model posits that disability is not caused by an individual's physical or mental limitations, but by the social structures and attitudes that fail to accommodate diversity. In the context of inclusive education, the Social Model emphasises the need for systemic change, including inclusive curricula, teacher training, accessible infrastructure, and attitudinal transformation, to create enabling environments for all learners (Shakespeare, 2006). This model aligns with the role of community-based social work, which seeks to remove societal barriers and empower marginalised groups through advocacy, education, and community engagement.

Applying the Social Model in Ibadan allows for a critical examination of how social norms, institutional practices, and policy gaps contribute to the exclusion of children with disabilities from mainstream education. It also offers a framework for evaluating the effectiveness of community-based interventions in dismantling these barriers. For instance, by promoting disability awareness campaigns, facilitating inclusive teacher training, and advocating for infrastructural adjustments, social workers contribute to transforming schools into inclusive spaces. Moreover, the Social Model supports the idea that inclusion is not about "fixing" the child but about restructuring the educational system to accommodate diverse learners (Goodley, 2011). This paradigm is especially relevant in the Nigerian context, where cultural misconceptions about disability often lead to stigmatization and neglect (Obi, 2017). Social workers, using the principles of the Social Model, can challenge these narratives and advocate for systemic changes that uphold the rights and dignity of children with disabilities.

Methodology

This study adopted a **qualitative research design**, specifically a **descriptive case study approach**, to explore the implementation of inclusive education and the role of social workers in facilitating access and support for children with disabilities in Nigeria. The qualitative approach was deemed appropriate because it enables an in-depth understanding of experiences, perceptions, and contextual realities surrounding inclusive education, particularly in under-resourced settings such as Ibadan (Creswell & Poth, 2018).

Study Area and Population

The study was conducted in **Ibadan Metropolis, Oyo State, Nigeria**, a region known for its educational institutions and diverse socio-economic demographics. The population for this study included **teachers, social workers, school administrators, and parents of children with disabilities** across both public and private inclusive schools.

Sampling Technique and Sample Size

A **purposive sampling technique** was employed to select participants who are directly involved in inclusive education practices. This non-probability sampling method is appropriate for qualitative studies, especially when targeting individuals with specific knowledge or experience relevant to the research objectives (Palinkas et al., 2015). The sample comprised **20 participants**: 5 social workers, 5 teachers, 3 school heads, and 7 parents of children with disabilities from four inclusive education centers in Ibadan: HLA Special Education School, School for the Handicapped Sharp-Corner, Omoyeni School for the Handicapped, and AIKEA Special School and Home.

Data Collection

Data was collected using semi-structured interviews and four focus group discussions (FGD) sessions. The interviews provided individual perspectives on inclusive education practices and the contributions of social workers, while the four FGDs facilitated group-level insights on shared challenges and community-based strategies for supporting children with disabilities. All interviews and FGD sessions were conducted in English and Yoruba, depending on participants' preferences, and were audio-recorded with informed consent.

Data Analysis

Thematic analysis was used to analyze the qualitative data. Audio recordings were transcribed verbatim and coded using **Braun and Clarke's (2006)** six-step framework for identifying themes and sub-themes related to implementation challenges, social work interventions, and community involvement in inclusive education.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from a relevant institutional review board. Participants were informed of the study's objectives and their right to withdraw at any time. Anonymity, confidentiality, and voluntary participation were strictly observed (Orb, Eisenhauer, & Wynaden, 2001).

Thematic Analysis of Findings

Using Braun and Clarke's (2006) thematic analysis method, the interview data was transcribed and coded to generate recurring themes. The major themes that emerged include: (1) Understanding of Inclusive Education, (2) Challenges in Implementation, (3) Role of Community-

Based Social Work, (4) Inter-agency Collaboration, and (5) Recommendations for Policy and Practice.

Understanding of Inclusive Education

Many respondents had a conceptual understanding of inclusive education, though interpretations varied based on roles and institutions.

Respondent 1 (Teacher)

“Inclusive education means allowing children with disabilities to learn with others in a regular classroom. It’s not just about bringing them in, it’s about making them feel part of the class.”

Respondent 2 (Administrator)

“For us, inclusion is not only physical placement but also emotional and social integration. If the child is in the school but is isolated, then inclusion has failed.”

Some parents, however, were unfamiliar with the term “inclusive education” but supported its principles.

Respondent 3 (Parent)

“All I want is for my child to be accepted and taught like every other child. They should not be left behind because of their condition.”

Challenges in Implementation

Almost all stakeholders acknowledged several obstacles to achieving inclusive education in Ibadan.

Respondent 4 (Social Worker)

“The schools are trying, but we lack the basic facilities—ramps, assistive technology, special teaching aids. It’s a tough situation.”

Respondent 5 (Teacher)

“There’s no consistent training for teachers. Most of us learn on the job. We need regular workshops and exposure.”

Respondent 6 (Parent):

“Some teachers don’t want to teach children with disabilities. They say it’s extra work.”

Overcrowded classrooms, inadequate funding, and social stigma were also cited frequently.

3. Role of Community-Based Social Work

Community-based social workers were reported to be pivotal in supporting inclusive practices in schools and communities.

Respondent 7 (Social Worker)

“Our job is to connect families with resources, speak to teachers and educate them, and also to challenge harmful attitudes in communities.”

Respondent 8 (Administrator)

“We work with social workers during outreach and awareness campaigns. They help to educate families that inclusion is possible.”

Several participants stressed that social workers often act as advocates for children with disabilities, ensuring their rights are respected within the educational system.

Respondent 9 (Social Worker)

“I’ve had to write letters to education boards, accompany parents to meetings, and follow up with teachers. It’s all about ensuring that the child is not forgotten.”

Inter-agency Collaboration

Many stakeholders emphasized the importance of partnerships between schools, NGOs, religious bodies, and government agencies.

Respondent 10 (Administrator)

“The Ministry of Education helps, but it’s irregular. The NGOs and churches fill the gap with donations and training workshops.”

Respondent 11 (Teacher)

“The community can be powerful when they are properly engaged. When parents, religious leaders, and social workers come together, real change happens.”

Recommendations for Policy and Practice

Stakeholders had varied but insightful recommendations to strengthen inclusive education in Ibadan.

Training and Capacity Building:

“Teachers should be trained continuously. You can’t do inclusive education with ignorance.” — Respondent 12 (Teacher)

Provision of Infrastructure:

“We need assistive devices, ramps, toilets that are accessible. These things make learning possible.” — Respondent 13 (Parent)

Community Sensitization:

“There is still a lot of stigma. Some people think children with disabilities are cursed. That mindset must change.” — Respondent 14 (Social Worker)

Policy Enforcement:

“The policies exist on paper, but implementation is where we struggle. Government must monitor schools better.” — Respondent 15 (Administrator)

Key Patterns and Interpretations

a. Inclusive Ideals vs. Realities

While stakeholders are mostly aligned with the ideals of inclusive education, there is a wide gap between policy and implementation. This reinforces previous findings by Ajuwon (2008) and Eleweke and Rodda (2002), who noted that Nigerian schools often lack the resources and personnel to support meaningful inclusion.

b. Social Work as an Inclusion Catalyst

Community-based social work was found to be an enabling factor in promoting inclusive education. Through advocacy, family support, and school engagement, social workers help bridge

the gap between systemic shortcomings and grassroots needs echoing Mmatli's (2008) assertion that social workers are essential in transforming inclusive ideals into actionable practices.

c. Resource Inequality

Disparities between public and private schools were a common concern. Private institutions are more likely to possess teaching aids, trained staff, and functional buildings, though they remain unaffordable for many. This duality entrenches inequality and necessitates strategic resource redistribution.

d. Cultural and Societal Stigma

Negative attitudes towards disability remain a powerful barrier. Several respondents reported that teachers, parents, and community members sometimes hold beliefs that hinder the integration of children with disabilities. This aligns with the cultural findings of Abang (2005) and Ozoji (2015), who underscored the need for sustained community education and engagement.

e. Sustainability of Community-Based Initiatives

Though commendable, community-based interventions often depend on temporary donor support. Respondents advocated for systemic inclusion of these models into national education and social protection strategies to ensure sustainability.

Discussion

The findings of this study illuminate the multifaceted challenges and opportunities associated with implementing inclusive education in Nigeria, particularly within the context of Ibadan. The perspectives of teachers, social workers, school administrators, and parents provide a comprehensive understanding of the systemic barriers and facilitators impacting the educational experiences of children with disabilities.

Understanding of Inclusive Education

The study reveals a general awareness among stakeholders—teachers, school administrators, social workers, and parents about the principles and intent of inclusive education. Most respondents acknowledged that inclusion goes beyond the mere physical placement of children with disabilities into mainstream classrooms. Instead, they emphasized a broader, more holistic interpretation that incorporates the social, emotional, psychological, and academic integration of learners with diverse needs. This aligns with the definition provided by Ajuwon (2008), who asserted that inclusive education is about creating a learning environment where every child, regardless of ability or disability, is given equal opportunity to participate, learn, and thrive. According to him, inclusion must not only address access to classrooms but must also ensure that teaching practices and school environments are modified to meet the diverse needs of all learners. This comprehensive understanding among respondents in the present study mirrors findings from international literature which emphasize that effective inclusive education promotes equity, participation, and a sense of belonging among all students (UNESCO, 2009). Teachers and administrators in Ibadan who participated in the study expressed support for the principles of

inclusive education, recognizing that children with disabilities deserve to be educated alongside their peers in general education settings. Many noted that this practice can help foster socialization, reduce stigmatization, and build empathy among students. The positive outlook expressed by these stakeholders underscores a growing cultural shift towards more inclusive norms within some educational institutions.

Despite improving awareness, the study uncovers inconsistencies in how inclusive education is practiced. Some educators view inclusion as only physical access, neglecting necessary pedagogical adjustments. This gap between policy and implementation is similarly noted in Nigerian studies due to a lack of a unified vision of inclusive education among stakeholders (Eleweke & Rodda, 2002).

This inconsistency points to a critical need for structured and standardized training programs that provide educators and school administrators with the theoretical knowledge and practical skills required to implement inclusive practices effectively. Ajuwon (2012) emphasizes that without proper training, teachers are likely to feel overwhelmed or ill-prepared to address the diverse needs of students with disabilities, which can lead to resistance or passive exclusion. Moreover, training needs to cover differentiated instruction, diverse classroom management strategies, and assistive technology use. In-service sessions, workshops, and collaborations with special educators aid mainstream teachers in gaining confidence and skills in inclusive teaching. In addition to training, the study highlights the importance of clear policy guidelines for consistent implementation of inclusive education in Nigerian schools. Currently, many schools lack a comprehensive framework for including children with disabilities. This lack of guidelines leads to varied interpretations and approaches that may not benefit the learners (Okoli, 2019). Policymakers need to prioritize developing and sharing adaptable yet detailed inclusive education guidelines to help schools create supportive, accessible, and fair learning environments.

Furthermore, inclusion should be treated not only as a pedagogical concern but as a social justice issue that involves the entire community teachers, families, local government authorities, social workers, and civil society. Achieving a unified understanding of inclusive education requires collaborative efforts, ongoing dialogue, and a shared commitment to dismantling barriers that prevent full participation of children with disabilities in educational settings. Only through such collective action can inclusive education in Nigeria move from rhetoric to meaningful and sustainable practice.

Challenges in Implementation

The implementation of inclusive education in Ibadan and other parts of Nigeria faces numerous challenges, such as infrastructural limitations, resource shortages, inadequate teacher training, and societal stigma. These obstacles impede the actualization of inclusive education policies. Despite the Nigerian government's recognition of the rights of children with disabilities to inclusive education in the National Policy on Education, the practical situation often contradicts its intentions (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2013).

In Ibadan, public schools face significant infrastructure challenges, such as overcrowded, poorly ventilated classrooms that are not suitable for students with disabilities. Lack of ramps, wide doors, and accessible toilets hinders inclusion. Eleweke and Rodda (2002) note similar issues in developing countries, limiting disabled students' access to mainstream education. Schools in Ibadan struggle to accommodate students with mobility, visual, or hearing impairments, excluding them from regular learning opportunities.

The lack of specialized teaching materials and assistive technologies is closely tied to infrastructural challenges in schools. Limited access to basic aids like Braille books, audio devices, sign language resources, and tailored learning tools hinders inclusive education. Without these resources, teachers often rely on traditional methods that fail to support diverse learning needs, as emphasized by Ajuwon (2008). Insufficient materials not only hinder student engagement but also fuel their marginalization and lower academic performance.

General education teachers in Ibadan lack formal training in inclusive education, leaving them ill-equipped to support students with disabilities. The absence of key strategies such as differentiated instruction and inclusive assessment compromises education quality for learners with special needs. Ajuwon (2012) emphasized that teacher readiness is crucial for inclusive education success, requiring structured training programs. Unfortunately, Ibadan and other parts of Nigeria often lack comprehensive inclusive education modules in teacher training programs, perpetuating educator unpreparedness.

Social stigma, misconceptions, and cultural influences hinder inclusion efforts for children with disabilities, impacting their enrolment in mainstream schools and overall well-being (Eleweke & Rodda, 2002; Nwazuoke & Igbo, 2015). In Ibadan, despite awareness campaigns, myths and religious beliefs still affect how disabilities are perceived.

Moreover, the shortage of special education personnel, like speech therapists and occupational therapists, hampers inclusive education. These professionals are crucial for supporting learners and teachers, providing interventions, and enabling students with disabilities to engage fully. Their absence widens the educational disparity, as highlighted by Ajuwon (2008), who noted that the lack of a diverse support system in schools undermines program inclusiveness and effectiveness.

To address these challenges, there is a critical need for systemic reforms that prioritize inclusive education in teacher training, funding for assistive technologies, and public awareness. Policies must turn into practical strategies with clear responsibilities and monitoring. Collaboration with social workers and NGOs, particularly in places like Ibadan, can bridge the gap between policy and practice, mobilizing support, training teachers, and advocating for resources to realize inclusive education for all children.

Role of Community-Based Social Work

Community-based social workers play a pivotal role in bridging the gap between policy and practice in inclusive education. Their involvement in advocacy, family support, and community sensitization efforts is crucial for fostering an inclusive environment. Mmatli (2008) emphasizes

the importance of social workers as agents of change who can mobilize community resources and challenge societal norms that hinder inclusion. The study's findings corroborate this perspective, highlighting the effectiveness of social workers in facilitating collaborations between schools, families, and communities to support children with disabilities.

Inter-agency Collaboration

Effective implementation of inclusive education requires coordinated efforts among various stakeholders, including government agencies, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), religious institutions, and community leaders. The study identifies successful partnerships that have led to improved access to learning aids, teacher training, and increased awareness about inclusive practices. However, these collaborations are often limited in scope and sustainability. There is a pressing need for institutionalized frameworks that promote ongoing inter-agency cooperation to ensure the longevity and scalability of inclusive education initiatives (Ajuwon, 2008).

Recommendations for Policy and Practice

Based on the study's findings, several recommendations emerge to enhance the implementation of inclusive education in Nigeria:

1. **Teacher Training and Professional Development:** Integrate comprehensive inclusive education modules into teacher training curricula to equip educators with the necessary skills and knowledge. Continuous professional development programs should be established to update teachers on best practices and emerging trends in inclusive education (Ajuwon, 2008).
2. **Infrastructure and Resource Allocation:** Invest in the development of accessible school infrastructure, including ramps, specialized classrooms, and assistive technologies. Adequate funding should be allocated to procure teaching materials tailored to the needs of students with disabilities (Eleweke & Rodda, 2002).
3. **Community Engagement and Sensitization:** Implement community-based awareness campaigns to challenge negative stereotypes and promote positive attitudes towards individuals with disabilities. Engaging religious and traditional leaders can be instrumental in shifting cultural perceptions and fostering inclusive communities (Mmatli, 2008).
4. **Policy Enforcement and Monitoring:** Establish robust monitoring and evaluation mechanisms to assess the implementation of inclusive education policies. Regular audits and feedback loops can help identify gaps and inform policy adjustments to enhance effectiveness (Ajuwon, 2008).
5. **Strengthening Inter-agency Collaboration:** Develop formal partnerships among government bodies, NGOs, educational institutions, and community organizations to coordinate efforts and share resources. Such collaborations can lead to more comprehensive and sustainable inclusive education programs (Ajuwon, 2008).

Conclusion

The journey towards achieving inclusive education in Nigeria is fraught with challenges, yet the commitment of stakeholders and the strategic involvement of community-based social workers offer a pathway to progress. Addressing infrastructural deficits, enhancing teacher capacity, and fostering community engagement are critical steps in creating an educational landscape that accommodates and celebrates diversity. By implementing the recommended strategies, Nigeria can move closer to realizing the goal of inclusive education, ensuring that all children, regardless of their abilities, have access to quality education and the opportunity to thrive.

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